

SHEAR-DOMINATED BENDING BEHAVIOR OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPOSITE LATTICE ISOBEAM STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Rectangular carbon/epoxy-composite lattice (IsoBeam™) structures were manufactured and tested in shear-dominated bending. The inherent complex geometry with interwoven joints required prepreg tows to be hand-placed on a pin-type mandrel. Three IsoBeam structures nominally 6 in. (152.4 mm) high by 3 in. (76.2 mm) wide by 2 ft (0.61 m) long with 4 bays [each 6 in. (152.4 mm) long] weighing 1.82-1.86 lbs (8.09-8.27 N) were created. Longitudinal and diagonal members, consolidated with half-spiral aramid sleeves, were 0.4 in. (10.2 mm) and 0.2 in. (5.1 mm) in diameter, respectively. The IsoBeam specimens – tested in three- and four-point bending – were dominated by shear due to the short beam length-height ratio. An average maximum transverse load of 4.11 kips (18.3 kN) provided an equivalent beam shear strength of 2.06 kips (9.15 kN) with a bending moment of 20.2 kip-in (2.29 kN-m). This compares to a linear finite-element analysis prediction of 34 kips (151 kN). The low strength is attributed to a combination of marginal material quality, insufficient member consolidation, and inadequate tension on the tows during manufacturing.

After beam failure, individual undamaged members were examined and tested separately. Fiber-volume fractions averaged only 38%, and void contents averaged 4.3% and 6.4% in diagonal and longitudinal members, respectively. Although diagonal members exhibited higher compression strength [111 ksi (767 MPa)] than longitudinal members [62.5 ksi (431 MPa)], the overall average compression strength of 86.9 ksi (599 MPa) and modulus of 17.8 Msi (122 GPa), were substantially lower than observed in related research.

This research demonstrated that IsoBeam structures absorb considerable energy after initial failure, exhibiting ductility and damage tolerance, due to redundancy. Inner diagonals are significantly stiffer than outer diagonals and exhibit higher strains. Improving manufacturing quality should yield light-weight IsoBeam structures that are strong, ductile, and damage tolerant.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper describes an experimental investigation of the structural characteristics of hand-manufactured IsoBeam™ structures – rectangular, composite lattice structures (see Figure 1) – loaded in transverse, shear-dominated bending. The research addresses and achieves the following objectives: 1) Define the process for weaving and consolidating an IsoBeam structure by hand; 2) Analytically predict the strength of a properly manufactured and consolidated IsoBeam; 3) Determine the characteristics of a carbon/epoxy IsoBeam structure loaded transversely to failure; 4) Compare member compression strength, void content and fiber volume fraction of hand-woven members to machine-woven members; and, 5) Quantify the quality of hand-manufactured IsoBeam specimens.

To address these objectives, a finite element model of the beam was created and three unidirectional carbon/epoxy IsoBeam structures were manufactured by hand and tested in short-beam shear-dominated bending. The process for weaving and consolidating an IsoBeam structure by hand are described briefly here, and in more detail in Hinds [1]. Individual members were cut from each specimen, sanded, inspected under the microscope to quantify void percentage and fiber volume

fraction, tested in axial compression, and compared to similar tests on members manufactured with spiral sleeves on a 3-d braiding machine [2-3]. This research provides an initial evaluation of the quality of hand-manufactured, composite structures to be utilized in beam applications. Suggestions are also made for improving the quality of hand-manufactured IsoBeam specimens.

Figure 1: This is a model of an IsoBeam structure.

The IsoBeam specimens were designed for flexure because bending is common in beam applications, but due to complications fabricating long IsoBeam structures by hand, they were too short to exhibit classical bending behavior. Thus, the beams – tested in bending – were dominated by shear due to their short length to height aspect ratio.

Composite structures provide substantial strength and stiffness with light-weight characteristics. Composite IsoTruss® structures, consisting of unidirectional composite members with interwoven joints, enhance this behavior [4]. The IsoBeam™ is a derivative of a composite IsoTruss lattice structure in the shape of a rectangular beam with members intersecting at nodes. The IsoBeam provides comparable benefits to the basic IsoTruss, mainly the open lattice structure, redundancy and high strength-to-weight ratio, but may be used in applications, where a rectangular cross-section is preferred. This rectangular shape enables more applications of the basic underlying composite lattice structure, the IsoTruss, where flat upper and lower surfaces are needed or desired. These applications include bridge decks, truck beds, airplane wing boxes and floor beams, or any beam where there is an economical advantage to reducing weight.

To create a composite IsoBeam™ structure, the underlying structure, (IsoTruss) can be slightly distorted to create a similar structure, but with a rectangular cross-sectional shape. The IsoBeam geometry is created from a 6-node double-grid IsoTruss where four of the nodes are shifted vertically so they are on the same top and bottom plane (shown in Figure 2 with 6-node double-grid IsoTruss and IsoBeam profiles). This shifts longitudinal fibers further away from the neutral axis, increasing the moment of inertia, by a factor of 1.48 over the 6-node double-grid IsoTruss with 12 longitudinal members and by 5.85 over a single-grid 6-node IsoTruss with 6 longitudinal members [5]. Conversely, going from a 6-node single-grid IsoTruss to an IsoBeam adds substantial manufacturing complexity due to the longitudinal member being on the most outer plane of the IsoBeam. This manufacturing complexity is similar to complexity seen in double-grid IsoTruss structures.

Figure 2: End view of 6-node double-grid IsoTruss (left) and IsoBeam (right) structures (arrows on IsoTruss indicate shifting required to convert into IsoBeam).

2 ISOBEAM DESIGN

The IsoBeam consists of longitudinal and diagonal members (see Figure 3). The longitudinal members are the six straight members that run along the length of the beam on the top and bottom. The diagonal members in a conventional IsoTruss are referred to as helicals, since they create a piecewise-linear helical pattern around the longitudinal members. The diagonal members of the IsoBeam act and look more like traditional diagonal members in truss structures, hence the name.

- Primary Node
- ▲ Vertical Anti-node
- ◆ Interior Anti-node
- Horizontal Anti-node

Figure 3: IsoBeam Structure with Labeled Nodes: A) Side view; B) Top view; and, C) End view.

Longitudinal members in IsoBeam structures carry axial and bending loads while diagonal members carry transverse shear and torsion, each via axial compression or tension in a member. Interweaving members at intersections increases stability by shortening local buckling lengths. A single-grid IsoTruss can be filament wound [6], but the IsoBeam has members surrounding the inner diagonal members like a double-grid IsoTruss. This requires a complex process of manufacturing by hand (as done in this research) or use of a special 3-dimensional braiding machine [7-8].

There are three different groups of diagonal members: outer diagonal members in vertical planes, outer diagonal members in horizontal planes, and inner diagonal members. The vertical outer diagonal members lie in vertical planes on the left and right sides of the IsoBeam, forming an X-shape every

bay. The horizontal outer diagonal members lie in horizontal planes on the top and bottom of the structure, also forming an X-shape every bay. The inner diagonal members are inside the structure and consist of four diagonal members intersecting to create an interwoven joint at mid-height that creates an essentially rigid (i.e., fully three-dimensionally constrained) joint. There are two pairs of four inner diagonal members in every bay of the IsoBeam.

3 ISOBEAM MANUFACTURING

A mandrel designed and constructed by Jarvis was modified to create the IsoBeam specimens [5]. The mandrel was coated with Kiwi® neutral shoe wax to aid in removal of the cured specimen. Fabrication of the IsoBeam specimens was accomplished by positioning prepreg tows of Toray T700-12K-50C carbon fiber and TCR Composites UF3369-100 epoxy resin [9] onto a pin-style mandrel. Winding patterns were developed to simplify placement of the tows while achieving considerable interweaving of the 93 longitudinal tows with the 21 inner and 29 outer diagonal tows. The individual members were hand-wrapped with open spiral sleeves using DuPont 49-7100 denier aramid to consolidate members and eliminate voids. The inner diagonal members were completed and consolidated before adding the outer diagonal members (see Figure 4). Ideally, the inner and outer diagonal tows would be interwoven, but that would require an incredibly complex winding pattern which is difficult to accomplish by hand (although such a pattern is relatively straight-forward using a three-dimensional braiding process with an external hook system). During fiber placement and consolidation, a continuous 5 lbs (22 N) of tension was desired, but this was also difficult to monitor and maintain since the tension was applied by hand. Each beam required approximately 30 hours to fabricate by hand. The beams were cured in an oven for 1.5 hours at 250 °F (121° C) per the resin manufacturer's recommendations [9], with a 5° F (15° C) per minute ramp rate, using an embedded Type-T thermocouple to monitor the internal temperature.

Figure 4: Photo of Hand-Consolidated Inner Diagonal Members on IsoBeam Mandrel

The completed specimens were nominally 2 ft. (0.61 m) long with four 6 in. (152 mm) bays, 6 in. (152 mm) high and 3 in. (76.2 mm) wide, and weighed 1.833 lbs. (8.15 N), 1.824 lbs. (8.11 N) and 1.857 lbs. (8.26 N), respectively. The longitudinal and diagonal member diameters were nominally 0.4 in. (10.2 mm) and 0.2 in. (5.1 mm), respectively. Inner diagonal members – braced in all three directions – are stiffer than outer diagonal members, so the outer diagonal members were made slightly larger to enable them to carry more load.

4 THREE-POINT BENDING TESTS

The first beam was tested in 4-point bending, but the ends of the IsoBeam proved to be too flexible to prevent support rotation. Subsequent beams were tested in 3-point bending with a single top plate and roller system that interfaced directly with the swivel head and two bottom base plates with roller systems mounted 12 in. (305 mm) apart, as shown in Figures 5 and 6. Six string potentiometers were attached to metal rods epoxied to the inside bottom of the bays in line with the applied load and reaction points to measure deflections.

Figure 5: Schematic of Three-Point Bending Test Setup: A) Front View; and, B) Side View

Figure 6: Photo of Three-Point Bending Test Setup

5 THREE-POINT BENDING TEST RESULTS

5.1 IsoBeam Load-Displacement Test Results

The average maximum load was 4.11 kips (18.3 kN), although improvements in manufacturing and testing showed a progressive improvement exceeding 30% (see Table 1), and the average deflection at maximum load was 0.595 in. (15.1 mm).

Table 1: Maximum Load and Deflection for All IsoBeam Tests

Test	Bending Test Method	Max Load		Deflection at Max Load		Notes
		[kip]	[kN]	[in]	[mm]	
1A	4-Point	3.71	16.5	0.622	15.8	Local End Failure
1B	4-Point	3.69	16.4	0.556	14.1	Local End Failure
2A	3-Point	3.36	14.9	0.582	14.8	Fixture Slippage
2B	3-Point	4.71	20.9	0.578	14.7	Beam Failure
3	3-Point	5.10	22.7	0.638	16.2	Beam Failure
	Average	4.11	18.3	0.595	15.1	
	Std. Dev.	0.747	3.32	0.0338	0.857	
	[%]		18.2		5.67	

The load vs. displacement plots for all IsoBeam tests are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Load vs. Displacement Plots for all IsoBeam Tests

5.2 IsoBeam Moment-Displacement Test Results

The moment versus displacement plots are shown in Figure 8. The average maximum moment was 12.3 kip-in (1.39 kN-m) and the average maximum shear was 2.06 kips (9.15 kN). The average toughness (area under moment vs. deflection curve) was 20.0 kip-in² (57.3 N-m²).

Figure 8: Moment vs. Displacement Plots for all IsoBeam Tests

The results of Test 2B and 3 – the most carefully controlled tests – are summarized in Table 2. These averages are most representative of the actual capacity of the IsoBeam specimens in this research. Test 3 was the most carefully controlled test and yielded the highest capacity at 5.10 kips (22.7 kN).

Table 2: Summary of Test 2B and 3 IsoBeam Specimen Results

Test	Deflection at Max		Max Moment		Max Shear		Max Load	
	[in]	[mm]	[kip-in]	[kN-m]	[kip]	[kN]	[kip]	[kN]
2B	0.578	14.7	14.1	1.60	2.35	10.5	4.71	20.9
3	0.638	16.2	15.3	1.73	2.55	11.3	5.10	22.7
Average	0.608	15.4	14.7	1.66	2.45	10.90	4.90	21.8
Std. Dev.	0.0424	1.08	0.83	0.09	0.138	0.61	0.275	1.23
[%]	6.98		5.6		5.6		5.6	

5.3 Local Member Compression Test Results

The average local member compression strength was 86.9 ksi (599 MPa) with a corresponding strain of $5.31 \times 10^3 \mu\epsilon$ and an average Young's modulus of 17.8×10^6 psi (122 GPa) (see Table 3).

Table 3: Summary of Average Properties by Member Type

Member Type	Cross-Sectional Area		Compression Young's Modulus		Strain at Ultimate Compression Stress	Ultimate Compression Stress	
	[in ²]	[mm ²]	[10 ⁶ psi]	[GPa]	[10 ³ $\mu\epsilon$]	[ksi]	[MPa]
Longitudinal	0.121	77.8	20.8	143	3,392	62.5	431
Diagonal	0.0272	17.6	14.8	102	7,229	111	767
Average			17.8	122	5,310	86.9	599
Std. Dev.			4.24	29.2	2,714	34.5	238
[%]			23.9		51.1	39.7	

6 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS PREDICTIONS

6.1 Finite Element Model Description

A finite element model of the IsoBeam was made using Abaqus CAE to predict failure loads and validate experimental results. The model was a 4-bay IsoBeam with 160 members. The geometry, which matched the experimental beams, was created by drawing wire members between nodes and using B31 beam elements (three dimensional, linear beam elements between two nodes with six degrees of freedom: three translational and three rotational). The longitudinal members had a radius of 0.2 in. (5.08 mm) and the diagonal members had a radius of 0.1 in. (2.54 mm). The IsoBeam model was analyzed in three-point bending to facilitate comparison with the experiment results, based on axial load in each local member, maximum strain, and the Tsai-Wu stress-interaction failure criterion.

Material properties were obtained by adjusting values in an AGATE technical data sheet for T700 unidirectional tape [10] multiplied by a correction factor (ratio of the TCR properties to the AGATE properties) to match the limited properties in the TCR Composite T700/UF3369 technical data sheet [9] and provide the required stiffness and strength values. The axial compression stiffness [22 Msi (152 GPa)] and strength [139 ksi (958 MPa)] were adjusted to match related research [2-3].

The model was loaded with three point loads applied at the three top center nodes while the appropriate bottom nodes were constrained with pins and rollers, to represent the 3-point experimental testing. The model was determined to have converged when the strain changed by less than 1.0% after doubling the number of elements. The model mesh converged with a global element size of 2 in. (50.8 mm) which created two elements per diagonal member and three per longitudinal members.

6.2 Finite Element Predictions

The finite element analysis predicts failure when a total load of 34 kips (151 kN) is applied to the IsoBeam. The front, top, left outer diagonal in Bay 3 is the first member predicted to fail (based on Tsai-Wu) with an axial compression load of 4,260 lbs (19.4 kN) and a maximum strain of 6,084 $\mu\epsilon$. The distribution of the load among members is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Axial Load Diagram of Finite Element Analysis Results

The model was validated with simple hand calculations based on material properties and by comparing the analytical predictions to experimental results. Dividing the compressive strength of 139 ksi (958 MPa) by the stiffness of 22.3 Msi (152 GPa) indicates the strain at failure should be approximately 6,230 $\mu\epsilon$ – only 2% higher than the FEA prediction. The expected failure axial load was calculated by multiplying the area of the member by the compressive strength resulting in an expected axial load of 4,370 lbs (19.4 kN) for diagonal members, comparable to the FEA prediction.

Members with the highest Tsai-Wu values at failure are summarized in Table 4 as a function of member type. Longitudinal and horizontal outer diagonal members experienced lower loads, as expected, since bending is secondary in short beams. This agrees with experimental observations. Inner and vertical outer diagonal members are predicted to carry the highest loads, as expected. Vertical outer diagonals, however, should buckle, but are predicted to carry slightly more load (12.5%) than the inner diagonals (11.5%). During the experimental tests, the vertical outer diagonals also failed prior to the inner diagonals, but the failure involved buckling out of plane which was not predicted by the linear finite element analysis [11].

Table 4: Finite Element Analysis Predictions of Max Strain, Max Axial Load, and Critical Tsai-Wu Values for Each Member Type at IsoBeam Failure

Member Type	Member Strain [$\mu\epsilon$]	Member Axial Load [lbs (kN)]	Tsai-Wu	
Inner Diagonal	-5,779	-4,049	-18.0	0.94
V. Outer Diagonal	-6,084	-4,262	-19.0	1.00
H. Outer Diagonal	2,050	1,436	6.39	0.15
Longitudinal	-651	-1,825	-8.12	0.22

A simple hand analysis was performed to predict load distribution among the members. The inner diagonals have effective lengths that are approximately half that of the outer vertical diagonals. Using this ratio to approximate the load distribution, each inner diagonal should carry about 10% of the applied shear load while the vertical outer diagonals should carry about 5% each. This does not agree with the linear finite element analysis, but seems to agree with the experiment.

7 DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

7.1 Ductility

A noticeable trait is the ability of the specimens to continue to support load after damage. This ductility is mostly observed for Test 2B and Test 3 (Test 1B ended without observing this behavior). After reaching a peak load and sustaining damage, both test specimens exhibited a pattern of a large decrease in load followed by a subsequent increase until around 50% of the maximum strength where the load leveled off and then, slowly decreased. The tests were stopped and the specimens unloaded when this residual strength dropped to about 25% of the peak load, since the decline was gradual. The specimens were able to absorb a lot of energy and after unloading, returned to a nearly un-deformed state.

7.2 IsoBeam Quality

The average measured fiber volume fractions were only 40% and 35.4% in the longitudinal and diagonal members, respectively. These should have been at least 14% higher based solely on the fiber content, and even higher based on past experience. The disparity can be partially attributed to factors such as fraying during fabrication, broken fibers that appear as voids under the microscope, and measurement limitations.

Spiral sleeves without controlled tension do not provide adequate consolidation [12-14]. The diagonal members tested in compression had a higher strength (nearly double) than the much larger longitudinal members. The quality improved with each beam manufactured, but similar specimens from past research had both a higher compression strength and maximum strain to failure.

7.3 Comparison of Test Results to Related Research

Sika's results for carbon members wrapped with a half spiral sleeve of aramid indicated an average compression strength and stiffness of 139 ksi (958 MPa) and 22.3 Msi (147 GPa), respectively [2-3], with an average strain of 7,180 $\mu\epsilon$. As noted above, the average strength of 86.9 ksi (599 MPa) and average strain of 5,310 $\mu\epsilon$ are considerably lower than the averages from Sika, although some individual members approached the related strength results.

These unusually low strength values can be attributed to inadequate applied tension during fiber placement and consolidation, resulting in low fiber volume fractions and high void percentages. Another contributing factor is the material, which was out of specification with a low resin content while the material Sika used was within specification and had an overall better quality. Finally, Sika created simple, unidirectional members on a braiding machine under proper tension rather than creating them by hand as part of a complex geometry, as in the current research. Therefore, specimens created with an automated process are needed for further investigation.

7.4 Comparison of Test Results to Finite Element Predictions

The finite element analysis prediction of 34 kips (151 kN) suggests that the experimental maximum of 5.1 kips (22.7 kN) was only about 15% of the potential capacity [11,15]. Adjusting the FEA results to account for buckling, based on an assumed member end fixity of 2.5 – similar to that observed in related research – reduces the predicted beam strength to approximately 24 kips (107 kN). If the individual members were simply-supported at the joints, the prediction would drop to 9.6 kips (43 kN), which is too conservative, but still higher than observed. Thus, more experimental research is needed to understand this discrepancy.

The inner diagonal members carry more load than the vertical outer diagonal members. The longitudinal members did not catastrophically fail and continue to sustain load after damage. The weak link in shear is the flexibility (i.e., buckling) of the vertical outer diagonal members.

The 3-point test method works because the reaction forces were not applied directly to the end of the beam as in the 4-point tests. Forces cannot be applied directly to the end of the beam without local reinforcement. Also, the displacements of the top and bottom of the IsoBeam specimen are not equal during shear loading, due to deformation of the cross-section, and both should be measured.

8 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Conclusions

The quality of the hand-woven IsoBeam structures in this research was not inadequate, resulting in a lower overall strength than desired. This low strength is attributed to a combination of marginal material quality, insufficient member consolidation, and lack of adequate and continuous tension while placing tows and during consolidation.

A majority of the load under shear-dominated bending is transferred through the beam as axial compression loads in the inner diagonal members.

IsoBeam structures can exhibit ductile behavior, by absorbing substantial energy after ultimate load.

The characteristics exhibited by the IsoBeam structures are desired in beam applications, especially in aerospace and other weight-critical applications. The IsoBeam is a damage-tolerant system because of the many members which create redundant load paths. With proper manufacturing and consolidation, the IsoBeam should provide a strong, light-weight, ductile and fail-safe structure to be used in beam applications.

8.2 Recommendations

Future research should include improvements to manufacturing, testing of longer IsoBeam specimens, and nonlinear analysis. Shrink tape or other means of controlling pressure on the members should be used to consolidate IsoBeam members. A 3-dimensional braiding process should be developed and employed to fabricate IsoBeam structures. An IsoBeam structural configuration without vertical outer diagonal members should be investigated. A finite element analysis that includes local buckling should be performed.

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